

THE NOTION OF DISCOURSE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10370959>

Abstract: The main aim of this research is to study the notion of discourse and to analyze different standpoints and definitions about discourse by scientists.

Key words: discourse, verbal, non-verbal, text, speech

Studying the linguistic, social, cultural, anthropological, semiotic and pragmatic characteristics of private discourses found in certain layers of the language is one of the urgent problems of world linguistics today. Also, researching the scope of discourses found in literature and social spheres is one of the widely studied problems.

Since the 70s of the last century, the interests of linguists began to focus on the range of units larger than sentences. The beginning of interest in the discourse coincides with that period. But the history of the use of the term is a bit older: in the early 1950s, the American linguist Z. Harris called a text fragment larger than a sentence a discourse [1]. French linguist E. Benveniste used this term to express speech in the process of communication [2]. However, by the 70s, the researches of foreign linguists - U. Cheif, B. Deisler, J. Grimes, T. Dan Weiks formed discourse analysis as a new type of science.

Discourse theory and analysis is developing as a complex technological subject area in modern foreign linguistics. Analysis of the general and specific aspects of discourse is being conducted in such fields as text linguistics, psycholinguistics, semiotics, computer linguistics, translation studies, rhetoric, linguo-cultural studies, and in related fields such as philosophy, sociology, ethnology, political science, and jurisprudence. Research centers on discourse are at the University of California in Santa Barbara, USA (S. Thompson, U. Chafe, M. Mitun, P. Clancy, etc.), E. Shegloff at the University of California in Los Angeles, at the University of Oregon in Eugene (T. Givon, R. Tomlin, D. Payne), and in Europe it is available at the University of Amsterdam (T. van Dijk). Despite the different definitions given to discourse, there are aspects that unite these studies: discourse is a form of language manifestation in the context of living life. However, scientists have different opinions about its manifestation methods, specific manifestations and definitions given to them.

Although discourse is actively used not only in linguistics, but also in such fields as pedagogy, sociology, cultural studies, and jurisprudence, this term cannot be given a unanimous definition. The general description of the discourse and the

analysis of scientific research on its specific manifestations showed the great variety of views on this matter. For example: "Discourse is a written or spoken verbal product of communicative action" [3]; "Discourse is a complex communicative event that includes text and non-linguistic factors that affect its production and reception" [4]; "Discourse - a communicative situation containing the minds of communicators and a text created in the process of communication" [5]; "Discourse is a coherent text combined with extralinguistic, pragmatic and other factors obtained from events" [6]; "Discourse is a communicative event in which the space of conditional communication is implemented in a certain cognitive and typological way [7]."

Discourse is a consistent text consistently enriched with extralinguistic, socio-cultural, psychological and other factors; event-dependent graded text; interaction of people perceived as a purposeful social action and speech as a component of their mechanisms of consciousness (cognitive processes). Discourse is a speech "immersed in life". Therefore, the term "discourse", unlike the term "text", is not used in the most common definitions for ancient and other texts that do not directly restore links to living life [8].

G.K.Odilova argues that who conducted research on discourse in Uzbekistan: scientists J.SH. Safarov, L.R. Raupova, fellow scientists A.B. Tumanova, V.K. Sobirova and G.K.Odilova conducted research on discursive analysis in linguistics [9]. In the following years, works devoted to the Islamic discourse began to appear, although they were few in number. In the above studies, pragmatic, linguistic and cultural characteristics of Islamic discourse, problems of translation from Uzbek to English have not been studied. Semantic features of the Islamic-religious lexicon found in the Islamic discourse of various narrative and public styles in English have not been analyzed.

The first studies of discourse in Western linguistics were carried out in the 70s of the 20th century, this term was introduced to the science by the American linguist Z. Harris. Discourse has been interpreted in various ways in Western linguistics. Their standpoints have been presented in several scientific studies, but researchers have struggled to put these opinions into a single system and express their position firmly while giving a detailed definition of discourse. V. M. Undritsova, a Russian linguist, collects the best definitions of Western and Russian scientists about discourse in her candidate research and gives bold conclusions. For example, V. M. Undritsova's dissertation mentions the following thoughts of Van Dijk about discourse: "discourse is one of the characteristics of the context in a certain time and situation with the participation of a number of

social participants, in particular, the speaker/writer, listener/reader the process of entering into the resulting communicative dialogue. This communicative act can be written or spoken. Verbal and non-verbal communication can be observed in this process, which is mostly oral. Examples of this situation from everyday life include the communication processes that occur when having lunch with friends, in the communication between a doctor and a patient, and when reading the news in a newspaper [10]."

Barlet's views such as "discourse arises as a result of the frame around concepts or various situations", V.Z. Dem'yankov's views such as "discourse arises around a concept, its participants, background and in a specific situation", V. VKrasnykh's "discourse is created because not the text, it shrinks along with the activity, speech and thought process. Linguistic and extra-linguistic elements work equally in this process. Discourse-intrinsic linguistic and linguocognitive point of view is a phenomenon in the plan. In discourse, not only language, but also aspects of thinking in language come to light; N.N. Mironova's remarks that "discourse is an information unit saturated with linguistic and extralinguistic parameters", and E.N. Mishkurov, Y.V. Sidorov, N. VGrabovsky, A.A. Kibrik, while organizing the complementary controversial opinions, M.V. Udrisova, "discourse is a socially conditioned reality "speech, taken together with extralinguistic features of direction, is a complex communicative phenomenon".

Most of the world's scientists have tried to clarify the definition, formal structure and types of discourse, we will consider some of them. V. I. Karasik emphasizes that each discourse should consist of the following components:

1) participants; 2) chronotope; 3) goals; 4) values; 5) strategies; 6) material (topics); 7) diversity of genres and types; 8) present texts; 9) discursive formulas [11].

M.Stabs defines the discourse as follows: 1) a linguistic unit resulting from the size of the discourse fragments; 2) the content of the discourse is intrinsically dependent on the use of the language in the social context; 3) organizationally, the discourse is interactive and dialogic [12].

P.Serio interprets the discourse with the following concepts: 1) speech, that is, according to Saussure's theory, any form of speech; 2) text in the size of a phrasal unit; 3) from the pragmatic point of view, "discourse" refers to the effect of information (text) on the recipient (specific situation, addressee, and specific place); 4) in the third case, discourse means "dialogue", "conversation" and is considered a means of expressing an opinion; 5) according to Benevist, "discourse" refers to speech that does not need explanation; 6) expression of

language units in language and speech; 7) a set of communication units specific to a particular social group, for example, "administrative discourse", "feminist discourse"; 8) text analysis structure [13]. Discourse is a structure created for the study of the statement from the point of view of the discursive mechanism, that is, the study and research of the internal components of the text as a whole. Some linguists recommend studying discourse by dividing it into types. M.L. Makarov divides the discourse into three: 1) functional discourse - expression of speech in the process; 2) formal discourse - speech is reflected in oral or written text

3) situational discourse - research of the communicative process as a result of a specific situation, extralinguistic factors [14]. V. I. Karasik also divides the discourse into two - personal and institutional types. If the personal discourse occurs with the participation of close communicators, the institutional discourse is a discourse between individuals belonging to a social group [15]. A.V.Olyanich, who conducted a large-scale study on discourse and its presentation theory, considers discourse to be a phenomenon arising from the needs of people [16]. According to the scientist, different discourses have arisen precisely because of the different needs of mankind. So, it is a phenomenon that is updated over time. The mobile discourse that has arisen due to the need to use the Internet is a proof of this.

To conclude, discourse is a form of communication that is a combination of speech and non-verbal factors. Not every text can be a discourse. In our view, a text appears as a discourse when viewed in conjunction with external factors. In general, discourse is a problem of modern linguistic trends. However, no matter how diverse the views are, it is impossible not to distinguish the rationale core at the base of this diversity. This is determined by today's integrative state of linguistics and the nature of commonality.

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